

REQUIREMENTS FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: *Teaching has been an essential process in pedagogy demanding great effort and responsibility. Essentially teaching process becomes more difficult in teaching a foreign language to learners a language as a second language. My below written article is devoted to requirements for foreign language teaching*

Key words: *Secondary special vocational education, the goal of academic lyceums, teaching foreign languages. the communicative approach, practical trainings.*

The first law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" adopted in 1992 and the basis of the "National Program of Personnel Training" adopted on August 29, 1997, the economic, social, scientific-technical and cultural formation of a needy, creative, socially active, spiritually rich person and training of highly qualified competitive personnel. [2] Secondary special vocational education plays an important role in the system of continuing education of our country. Academic lyceums and vocational colleges directly contribute to the fact that our students are not indifferent to the future and choose a career in the future. While the goal of academic lyceums is to provide students with in-depth knowledge of disciplines and to raise a younger generation in higher education, the current goal of vocational colleges is to ensure that young people acquire one or more specialties in their chosen profession. [1]

The goal of the current attention and demands on foreign languages is to plan the process of teaching a foreign language. In the process of teaching foreign languages, special attention is paid to the development of the student's personality and abilities.

This can be clearly seen in vocational education institutions. The requirement for teachers is to ensure that every student in an educational institution learns a foreign language not as a science but as a profession. Of course, not every swimmer is good enough to be a linguist, and it is certain that he or she will have a profession. As an example, in this rapidly developing country, the instructions for use of imported equipment are written in a foreign language, which is not used by a foreign specialist or worker, it is used by our young professionals. And if the personnel trained by our professional colleges do not know their rules and manage, it means that the level of education in our country is in the background. After all, the strength of any state is determined by its spiritual maturity, the intellectual potential of its citizens. [3-13]

Therefore, the planning of lessons should create favorable conditions for the development of the learner, taking into account his natural intellectual potential, the teacher should take into account the goals, emotions, interests, views of the student, take into account the psychological and physiological characteristics of the student:

Teaching foreign languages is carried out through student interaction: [4-88]

- The teacher should be able to independently research, analyze, compare, modify, apply knowledge in the process of communication, in which the teacher should be the organizer, consultant and supervisor of the learning process;
- The organization of education in pairs and groups ensures high activity of students;

The communicative approach, which is recognized as a priority in modern foreign language teaching methods, is organized and controlled in the practical training aimed at teaching communication in foreign languages.

Practical trainings on the basics of foreign language teaching are organized in a planned interactive way, where students learn not as passive listeners, but in-depth understanding of the material studied, comparing them with the criteria in the native language, independent research and correct conclusions.

The technologicalization of the educational process in practical classes aimed at teaching communication in foreign languages is carried out through the conceptual principles of communicative approach, which is recognized as a priority in modern methods of teaching foreign languages.

Thanks to the positive attitude to foreign languages and fruitful work, these days young people studying in academic lyceums and professional colleges "Yangi Avlod" or "English B1" for first-year, second-year and third-year students "Student's book" and "Work book" is increasing its knowledge on the basis of textbooks. The advantage of the new generation of textbooks is that they are designed for our young language learners to use both on a daily basis and in a branched order.

References:

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